

Synthesis and Characterisation of Metal Complexes with Diacetylmonoxime(2-mercaptophenyl)imine and 2,3-Dimethyl-3-oxime(2-benzothiazoline)

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Direct reaction of 2-aminobenzenethiol and diacetylmonoxime does not yield any Schiff base. However the *in situ* reaction of these two constituents in the presence of metal salts like $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Na PdCl_4 and FeCl_3 , yielded complexes of 2,3-dimethyl-3-oxime(2-benzothiazoline) [HMOBTZ] of the type $[\text{M}(\text{HMOBTZ})\text{Cl}_2]$ where $\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} and Pd^{II} , and of those of the Schiff base diacetylmonoxime(2-mercaptophenyl)imine ($\text{H}_2\text{DAMOMPI}$) viz. $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{HDAMOMPI})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{HDAMOMPI})\text{Cl}_2]$

Schiff bases derived from 2-aminobenzenethiol and various diketones (such as glyoxal, biacetyl, benzil), together with their metal complexes have been reported¹⁻⁴. Reactions of 2-aminobenzenethiol with the diketones do not directly yield the corresponding Schiff bases as the main products; instead, bis-benzothiazolines are obtained in large yield. In the presence of metal ions, however, the thiazolines rearrange and form the normal Schiff base chelates. The bis-benzothiazolines are readily converted to the tautomeric Schiff bases by alkali or certain metal ions^{5,6}. So, there exists an equilibrium between the bis-benzothiazoline and the Schiff base. Some metal ions (such as Zn^{II}) react with the Schiff base tautomer and some others (like Cd^{II}) react by direct attack of the thiazoline.

Das *et al.*⁷ synthesised complexes of the type $(\text{MOPBTZ})_2$, where $\text{OPBTZ} = 2-(o\text{-hydroxyphenyl})$ benzothiazoline and $\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} . The thiazoline ligand in these complexes acts as a N-donor.

The metal complexes of the condensation products of 2-aminobenzenethiol and diacetylmonoxime have not been studied earlier. As an extension of our work on N, S donor ligands^{4,8,9}, we have synthesised the complexes of the ligand derived from the condensation of 2-aminobenzenethiol and diacetylmonoxime.

Results and Discussion

No Schiff base or thiazoline could be isolated when 2-aminobenzenethiol was allowed to react with diacetylmonoxime. But, the *in situ* reaction of the metal salts and the mixture of the two constituents gave the metal complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{HMOBTZ})\text{Cl}_2]$ (1), $[\text{Co}(\text{HMOBTZ})\text{Cl}_2]$ (2) and $[\text{Pd}(\text{HMOBTZ})\text{Cl}_2]$ (3) of bidentate ligand, 2,3-dimethyl-3-oxime(2-benzothiazoline) (abbreviated as HMOBTZ), which acts as a bidentate ligand, $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{HDAMOMPI})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ (4) and $[\text{Fe}(\text{HDAMOMPI})\text{Cl}_2]$ (5) complexes of the Schiff

base, diacetylmonoxime (2'-mercaptophenyl)imine (abbreviated as $\text{H}_2\text{DAMOMPI}$) which acts as a tridentate ligand. It, therefore, appears that the rearrangement of the thiazoline (HMOBTZ) to the Schiff base $\text{H}_2\text{DAMOMPI}$ is effected by Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} ions only in these reactions. The reactions are shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The conductance values support the formulations proposed. The diamagnetic nature of 1 and 3 suggests their square-planar environment. The magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} complex (4) is 1.28 B.M. This lowering of the magnetic moment value from the spin-only moment for one electron suggests strong exchange

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND UV SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					ΛM $\Omega^{-1}cm^2mol^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{max} cm^{-1}
		C	H	N	M	Cl			
1	[Ni(HMOBTZ)Cl ₂]	35.37 (35.53)	3.54 (3.55)	8.32 (8.29)	17.41 (17.38)	21.07 (21.02)	16.67	Dia.	^a 18 667
2	[Co(HMOBTZ)Cl ₂]	35.53 (35.50)	3.57 (3.55)	8.30 (8.27)	17.47 (17.43)	20.97 (21.01)	38.90	2.70	^b 20 000sh, 23 809sh, 35 714, 45 454 ^a 20 000
3	[Pd(HMOBTZ)Cl ₂]	31.10 (31.13)	3.13 (3.11)	7.29 (7.27)	27.64 (27.61)	18.39 (18.45)	40.99	Dia.	^a 24 390sh
4	[Cu ₂ (HDAMOMPI) ₂]Cl ₂	39.20 (39.22)	3.56 (3.59)	9.15 (9.15)	20.63 (20.75)	11.55 (11.60)	109.46	1.28	^c 4 390sh, 40 816 ^a 13 417
5	[Fe(HDAMOMPI)Cl ₂]	35.86 (35.93)	3.32 (3.29)	8.42 (8.38)	16.84 (16.77)	21.30 (21.25)	32.12	5.56	^c 13 986, 18 348, 19 607, 35 087, 43 478

*In DMF : compds. 1-3, 5, non-electrolyte ; 4, 1 : 2 electrolyte.

**Solvent : ^anujol, ^bmethanol, ^cdichloromethane.

interaction, supporting thereby the binuclear formulation. The magnetic moment value of 2.7 B.M. for the cobalt complex (2) suggests its square-planar geometry like other low-spin square-planar Co^{II} complexes. The Fe^{III} complex (5) shows the usual high-spin magnetic moment of five unpaired electrons.

Ir spectra : The ir bands at 3 440-3 200 cm⁻¹ for the complexes 1-3 can be assigned to ν_{OH} of the oxime group and this suggests that the oxime group is not deprotonated in the complexes. Bands at 3 140-3 080 cm⁻¹ are attributed to ν_{NH} which supports the complexation of the ligand in the thiazoline form. The ν_{NH} along with $\nu_{C=N}$ bands of the oxime group occur in the region 1 570-1 610 cm⁻¹. Based on the assignments of bands in Ni^{II}-diamine complexes¹⁰⁻¹² and Pd^{II}-amire complexes¹³⁻¹⁵, the bands of the present complexes in the region 520-510 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to ν_{M-N} modes. The ν_{M-Cl} modes appear at 430-330 cm⁻¹. No ν_{NH} mode is observed in 4 and 5 which suggests the participation of the ligand in the Schiff base form during complexation. However, the appearance of broad bands centred at 3 300 and 3 400 cm⁻¹ respectively, reveals that the oxime group is not deprotonated. The $\nu_{C=N}$ also appears as broad bands at 1 620 and 1 600 cm⁻¹ respectively. The presence of Fe-Cl bond in complex 5 is supported by the appearance of a band at 385 cm⁻¹¹⁶. A strong band at 315 cm⁻¹ for 4 is attributed to ν_{Cu-S} mode. Since this occurs at a lower frequency than that normally observed for ν_{Cu-S} modes, it is probable that sulphur atoms act as bridging¹⁶ ones, forming di-copper complex.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectral data of the complexes are shown in Table 1. The complexities associated with the energy-level ordering of the non-bonding orbitals prevent definite interpretation of the square-planar nickel(II) complexes¹⁷. However, it is a common practice to assign the first major band (near 20 000 cm⁻¹) to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ transition. Therefore, the band at 19 607 cm⁻¹ (in nujol) of the present Ni^{II} complex

is assigned this transition in square-planar geometry. Square-planar complexes of Co^{II} exhibit a band near 20 000 cm⁻¹^{18,19}. The ground state of low-spin cobalt(II) in a square-planar environment is probably $^1A_{1g}$ with configuration $eg^4 b_{1g}^2 a_{1g}^1$ ¹⁷. The spectra of [Co(HMOBTZ)Cl₂] (2) can then be assigned as a transition from these orbitals to the empty $b_{1g}(d_{x^2-y^2})$ -anti-bonding orbital. Other bands at 23 809, 35 714 and 45 454 cm⁻¹ are of charge transfer origin. The square-planar copper(II) complexes are known to exhibit two or more bands in the region 13 000-20 000 cm⁻¹¹⁷. In nujol, a band appears for the complex [Cu₂(HDAMOMPI)₂]Cl₂ (4) at 13 417 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder at 16 000 cm⁻¹. The bands at 18 348 and 19 607 cm⁻¹ for the complex [Fe(HDAMOMPI)Cl₂] (5) in dichloromethane suggest pentacoordination of the iron(III), as no such bands can be observed for a six-coordinate iron(III) complex due to spin-forbidden transitions²⁰. Other bands at 35 807 and 43 478 cm⁻¹ are of charge transfer origin.

Experimental

All the chemicals, solvents and reagents were of A.R. grade and they were purified and dried (whenever necessary) by usual procedures.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP8-150 spectrophotometer. Measurements of conductivity were made with a Philips PR-9500 conductivity bridge and magnetic susceptibility at room temperature with a Princeton 155 vibrating sample magnetometer.

Preparation of complexes : The free ligand could not be isolated in the pure state. The metal complexes were prepared by reacting 2-aminobenzenethiol, diacetylmonoxime and the metal salts in 1 : 1 : 1 molar proportion. To a boiling solution of 2-aminobenzenethiol (2.925 g, 23 mmol) in dry methanol (10 cm³), a solution of diacetylmonoxime

(2.36 g, 23 mmol) in minimum quantity of dry methanol was added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. A solution of the appropriate metal salt (23 mmol) in minimum quantity of dry methanol was then added to the boiling mixture, which was further refluxed for 6–8 h and then cooled. The complexes that separated out were washed with methanol. The copper complex, however, separated out on concentrating the cooled refluxate. The complexes were recrystallised, wherever possible, from methanol. The metal salts used were $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Na_2PdCl_4 , $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and anhydrous FeCl_3 .

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